

EUF EUROPEAN
UNIVERSITY
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European University Foundation

Annual Report

2019

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Overview

21 Network
full members
 and **34** associate members
 representing **30** countries

Funding programmes:

- Erasmus+
- Horizon 2020
- Connecting Europe Facility

95 Events
 attended

People reached with activities and projects

- From the network: **531** staff
- Erasmus Dashboard: **1,400** Higher Education Institutions and **3,000** staff accounts
- Online Learning Agreement: **40,000**
- OLAs, Erasmus+ App **80,000** downloads

28 Projects

8 Events
279 participants
 organised

4 Webinars
868 viewers

16 Staff
coworkers

A growing network

In 2019, the EUF Council of Rectors decided that the EUF will grow to encompass 100 members, becoming Europe's first super-network of universities in the process. This decision acknowledges the huge interest in being actively involved and contributing to the EUF activities that many universities have been expressing, as well as equip the EUF with the depth of expertise that will enable it to better advocate for the betterment of student mobility at the continental level, making sure its proposals accurately reflect a diversity of institutional priorities, organisational contexts and country-specific constraints.

Accordingly, 2019 was a year where the EUF network has grown at an unprecedented pace, welcoming 22 new universities from 15 countries. This increasingly vibrant community sees itself as a key driver for change and modernisation, working together to shape EU level policy, pilot and test new ideas through innovative projects and facilitating internal change processes that elevate the systemic impact of our joint activities.

Student mobility in a digital era

Working towards a more modern, efficient and digital management of student mobility has been a strategic vector of the EUF since 2015, and with the new programme period 2021-2027 fast approaching, 2019 was an important year to consolidate the work carried out by many EUF universities and plan ahead.

After unveiling the OLA in 2016, the Erasmus+ App in 2017 and the EWP network in 2018, the culmination of this work was the announcement made by the European Commission that all of these tools will be embedded in the next Erasmus programme. This pivotal step was announced in February 2019 during a webinar co-organised with the EUF and, according to a digital roadmap circulated to all Erasmus Charter holders, 2021 will be the year when all higher education institutions participating in Erasmus+ will be expected to start using common tools and standards for electronic data exchange.

The Erasmus+ digital roadmap aims to enable a better mobility experience, streamlining students processes, increasing quality of their stay abroad and facilitating data transactions between higher education institutions so that their staff members can spend more time on counselling students and academics. With this in mind, 2019 has brought forward a number of concrete developments:

- 450 higher education institutions connected to the EWP network
- +1400 higher education institutions with access to the Erasmus Dashboard
- +4400 international relation officers registered on the EWP Dashboard
- 40,000 Online Learning Agreements generated
- 80,000 downloads of the Erasmus+ mobile App

The EWP Competence Centre has played a central role in supporting this rapid growth, providing in-depth support documentation that comprises step-by-step guides, policy background documents, technical documentation, presentations and guidance videos, tutorials and much more.

Through a more structured cooperation with Erasmus+ National Agencies, and notably the Erasmus+ Digital Officers, all countries participating in the Erasmus+ programme have started to plan for the implementation of the Erasmus digital roadmap – which can be seen

through the fact that the Erasmus Going Digital events have received a lot of attention and National Agencies have started to organise events using this branding. For instance, our webinar with the EC attracted over 700 participants.

Projects: [Erasmus Without Paper](#) | [Online Learning Agreement](#) | [Erasmus+ mobile App](#)

Partnerships for start-up incubators and universities

The EU Council 2018 recommendation on key competences for lifelong learning states that “learners ought to undertake at least one practical entrepreneurial experience” which may include “creativity challenges, start-ups, student-led community initiatives, business simulations or entrepreneurial project-based learning” Accordingly, in 2019 several EUF member universities have joined forces to build structured partnerships with European incubators. These partnerships comprise the organisation of knowledge exchange events, working on the development of a digital platform, creating placement support materials for students and start-ups (toolkits, webinars, workshops), carrying out analysis about start-up needs, and opening opportunities for students to experience the start-up and incubator environment. Thanks to the established partnership with incubators, students can benefit from high-impact placement opportunities at start-ups.

Project: [POWER](#)

Internationalisation of doctoral training

The internationalisation of doctoral training has become a focus area of the network with three EU-funded projects contributing to this objective. In 2019, the creation of an interdisciplinary research and innovation community for early-stage researchers (ESRs), researchers and industry representatives has been pursued with the piloting of the [PhD Hub](#) portal; the international #PhDHubHack was officially kick-started with the hosting of a preparatory [online webinar](#); the analysis of how the Erasmus+ programme can best support the mobility of ESRs resulted in the testing of updated [Erasmus+ templates](#) as well as preliminary recommendations on how the new programme period 2021-2027 could meet the requirements of doctoral mobility; and preparatory work led to the successful incubation of a H2020 proposal on doctoral candidate skills' training. The shared engagement of the EUF and the European Commission to support the development of flexible models of cooperation and funding opportunities at doctoral level resulted in the organisation of [a joint session at EAIE 2019](#) together with the DocMob coordinating institution.

Projects: [European PhD Hub](#) | [DocMob](#) | [DocEnhance](#)

Staff training opportunities

The manifold roles played by teaching and administrative staff are essential to the success of the Erasmus+ programme. The EUF cooperated with several HEIs to analyse the missions and tasks of staff involved in international relations and student mobility, which helped to define the required competences of International Relation Officers.

Member universities have been leading working groups to carry out numerous researches, surveys, study visits, consultations with stakeholders, and training events with the aim to create solutions that add value to the competence development of staff members.

In 2019, the Framework for International Staff Competences, an interactive catalogue of teaching methodologies, and a comprehensive scientific research on quality teaching mobility have been already finalised. The training toolkit and guidelines on the enhancement of staff competences, the Erasmus+ Teaching and Training Mobility Platform and relevant policy recommendations on European level are expected to be completed in 2020

Projects: [FESC](#) | [TWE+](#)

Open Space 2019

From the 3rd to the 5th of July, the EUF Open Space took place in Versailles, France. The 3-day event, hosted by the University of Versailles Saint-Quentin-en-Yvelines, gathered over 70 participants from 23 European countries. The EUF's flagship Erasmus+ project incubator enabled participants to deepen their knowledge about Erasmus+ cooperation projects, notably Strategic Partnerships, Capacity Building, Knowledge Alliances as well as about the EC European Universities initiative. Our team and selected high-level guest speakers from the University of Alcalá, ELTE University, University of Paris-Saclay and the Erasmus Student Network provided

knowledge and expertise on several important topics related to the design, writing and evaluation processes of Erasmus+ Higher Education projects. The event brings Higher Education professionals together to develop their innovative project idea proposals. In addition, many networking opportunities ensure that participants strengthen their relations with their fellow academic and non-academic colleagues from all over Europe.

[OS 2019](#)

Towards the European Student Identifier

Enabling students to authenticate online in a reliable way means empowering them to take full advantage of their possibilities. In the digital world, paper-based credentials are of little help, and trust between users and service providers is paramount. This is especially true with regards to cross-border data exchange, where individuals and institutions often speak a different language and abide by different rules.

In this context, the MyAcademicID project is developing a ground-breaking solution for students to authenticate online in a safe and simple manner. This is made possible by bootstrapping essential digital infrastructure such as eIDAS and eduGAIN. Combined with the development of a unique European Student Identifier, different student electronic services for students going on mobility are just a click away. In practice, this translates into a truly European Student eID, valid across borders and e-services.

Students will also be able to register at higher education institutions using their national eID, linking their citizen and student identities.

Throughout 2019, the 13 project partners worked on identifying the key connections between the relevant networks and projects, specifying use-cases and engaging stakeholders at national and European level. The technical blueprint of the project, published in April 2020, is the result of transnational cooperation carried out through multiple project meetings, five technical workshops, two webinars with National Research and Education Networks (NRENs), and one European-level conference that welcomed more than 130 participants from 30 countries, including university CIOs, international relations officers, National Research and Education Networks, student unions, national and EU decision-makers, and identity and student service providers.

Project: [MyAcademicID](#)

Assessing the quality of partnerships amongst Higher Education Institutions

The increased awareness about the importance of data-informed policymaking and the quality of international partnerships is one of the core outcomes of the eQuATIC project and some of its [policy recommendations](#) were implemented in several Higher Education Institutions and at the level of the European Commission.

More than 150 institutions expressed interest in the eQuATIC tool, which allows to assess the quality of international mobility-enabling partnerships. Several institutions were also able to create their own reports on mobility-enabling partnerships following the instructions of the eQuATIC user documentation under the [EWP-Competence Centre](#).

Project: [eQuATIC](#)

Contributing to the modernisation of European higher education

In 2019, the network has once again successfully served as an incubator for project proposals that advance both the modernisation of the European higher education area and the strategic development of member universities. In total, 12 proposals were successfully submitted involving 9 Erasmus+ Strategic Partnerships, 1 Erasmus+ Forward-looking Cooperation project, 1 Horizon 2020 project, 1 Connecting Europe Facility proposal and 1 tender. An overview of the projects developed under the realm of the EUF network is available [here](#).

This year the EUF published a new policy paper which analyses how policy and technological developments can converge to enable the automatic recognition of credits earned abroad – a longstanding goal of the programme which is finally within reach, should there be enough ambition in designing its 2021-2027 incarnation. The automatic recognition policy paper is available [here](#).

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